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D-Pinitol: A Good Anti Diabetic

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Abstract

Through the ages humans relied on nature for their basic needs for production of food, clothing, medicine, etc. Plants are considered to be the factories where a cell is able to synthesize a vast variety of natural products as a result of various metabolic processes. Plant products are divided into two broad classes, primary and secondary metabolites. Primary metabolites for example carbohydrates, proteins, lipids etc facilitate growth and metabolism of plants whereas secondary metabolites like alkaloids, flavonoids and terpenoids which are the end products of primary metabolism are not so important for the basic life functions. Universally secondary metabolites are not found in every taxonomic groups but they are characteristic to a particular taxonomic group. These are mostly accumulated by plant cells in smaller quantities and synthesized in specialized cells at particular development stages thus, making their extraction and purification more difficult. Since the medicinal plants are rich in secondary plant products, these compounds are termed as 'medicinal' or 'bioactives'. Secondary metabolites have potent physiological effect on the mammals so they are considered as the active compounds of plants.

Keywords Bioactives, Secondary Metabolites, Tterpenoids, Flavonoids.

Introduction

Plants have formed the basis of sophisticated traditional medicine system that have been in existence for thousands of years and continue to provide mankind with new remedies. The use of plants in the Traditional systems of medicines dates back to empires of Mesopotamia, Egypt, Rome, China, India and many other cultures. Many bioactives are still used today for the treatment of ailments ranging from coughs and colds to parasitic infections and inflammation¹. Use of plants in Indian Ayurvedic system dates from before 1000 BCE (Charaka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita)^{2,3}. The essential role played by plant-based products in the healthcare has been extensively documented^{4,5}. Approximately 65% of the world's population rely mainly on plant-derived traditional medicines for their primary health care it has been estimated by World Health Organization.

Objective of study

D-pinitol is very commonly found in legumes, it is nontoxic and very safe antidiabetic agent which is found in nature so in this study pharmacological importance and characterization of D-pinitol is shown as this is largely responsible for antidiabetic property of a particular plant if present.

Review of Literature

D-Pinitol which is a good antidiabetic agent is isolated from many plants such as *Tamarindus indica* Linn., species of *Acacia*, *Cassia*, *Caesalpinia*, *Ceratonia* etc. Many publications have reported the strong activities of D-Pinitol as a natural antidiabetic⁶⁻⁹ and insulin regulator, but also as an active anti-Alzheimer, anticancer, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory, and is also immune- and hepato-protective¹⁰. This cyclohexitol occurs mainly in (+) form in certain leguminous plants. It is the 3-methyl derivative of inositol and found to exhibit antidiabetic¹¹, anti-inflammatory¹² and feeding stimulant activity¹³. Due to its antidiabetic properties its isolation from *Sesbania bispinosa* leaves has been patented¹⁴.

Main Text**Characterization of D-Pinitol**

It was isolated as a white powder from various plant parts and identified on the basis of detailed spectral studies:

D-pinitol whose m.p. is 185-86°C, was homogenous in TLC. Its analysis agreed with the molecular formula $C_7H_{14}O_6$. It did not respond to TNM test for unsaturation. It was insoluble in benzene, ethyl acetate, acetone and soluble in hot methanol and chloroform.

Fig 1: D-pinitol

Its infrared spectrum showed important absorptions at 3410, 3310 (O–H stretching of hydroxyl group), 1130 (C–O–C stretching of ether) and 1075 cm^{-1} (C–O stretching).

In the 1H NMR spectrum, a quartet integrating for two protons was observed at δ 3.92 which could be assigned to H-1 and H-6 protons. The appearance of a doublet of doublet at δ 3.76 was assignable to H-2 and H-5 protons. The H-4 and H-3 protons appeared as triplets at δ 3.62 and δ 3.29 respectively. A singlet at 3.66 appeared due to three protons of methoxy group. A multiplet at 3.34 appeared due to the presence of hydroxy protons.

Seven peaks were observed in ^{13}C NMR spectrum between 60.81-85.90 which indicates that oxygen is attached to all the carbons. The carbon with methoxy group attached (C-1) appeared most downfield as δ 85.93 whilst the carbons with an –OH group were observed at δ 72.56, 73.76, 72.04, 74.33 and 73.47 for carbons 2-6 respectively. The –OCH₃ carbon was observed at δ 60.80.

In the mass spectrum, the molecular ion peak was observed at m/z 194. The other important peaks were observed at 158 [$M^+ - H_2O$], 144 [$M^+ - (H_2O + MeOH)$] and 73 [$M^+ - (5H_2O - MeOH)$].

The compound thus appeared to be a cyclohexitol methyl ether. The location of the methoxy group was confirmed by the 2D NMR (COSY) spectrum, where the quartet at δ 3.92 (H-1, 6) appeared to be correlated with ddd (3.76-3.80, H-2, H-5). The triplet at δ 3.62 (H-4) was coupled with H-3 and H-5 protons.

Conclusion

Based on the above evidences, Compound was identified as the monomethyl ether of inositol, i.e. D-pinitol (Reported¹⁵ m.p. 184-85°C). The identity was finally confirmed by co-TLC with an authentic sample procured from Aldrich and preparation of pentaacetate, m.p. 97°C (Reported¹⁵ m.p. 98°C).

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